

Fig. 1. pH titration curves: (A) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.99 M NaClO₄, (B) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.01 M pyruvic acid+0.98 M NaClO₄, (C) B+0.01 M Mg²⁺, (D) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.01 M oxalic acid+0.96 M NaClO₄, (E) D+0.01 M Mg²⁺, and (F) 0.01 M HClO₄+0.01 M pyruvic acid+0.01 M oxalic acid+0.95 M NaClO₄.

and its values may be considered as a measure of the coordination tendency of L towards MA relative to M²⁺. The values of $\Delta \log K$ in the present work are positive in the case of oxalate as a primary ligand indicating a stabilisation of the ternary complexes which may be explained on the basis of the cooperative effect between the primary and secondary ligands¹. However, the negative values obtained in the citrate-pyruvate system may indicate a steric effect.

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Syntheses and Characterisations of some Rhenium Complexes with Biguanide and Methyl Biguanide

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COORDINATION complexes of protonated form of biguanides with Re^V were reported by Roy and Ray¹. In this paper we describe the isolation and characterisation of some Re^V complexes with neutral and protonated forms of biguanide and methyl biguanide. The biguanides act as bidentate chelating agent both in the protonated and in neutral forms giving two series of complexes, [ReOX(L)₂] and [ReOX(LH)₂]X₂ and [ReX₄(LH)₂]-X₂, where, X=OH⁻ or Cl⁻, and LH is the protonated form of biguanides. With biguanide itself, two more complexes [Re(OH)₂(LH)₂]Cl₂ and [Re(LH)₃](SO₄)₂·7H₂O have also been isolated. Biguanide complex of Re^{VII} in the protonated form has also been characterised. The compounds have been characterised on the basis of elemental, magnetic, conductivity and ir spectral data.

Experimental

Potassium hexachlororhenate, K₂ReCl₆, was prepared¹ from potassium perrhenate. Biguanide and methyl biguanide were prepared from dicyandiamide following standard method². All the other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of complexes :

[ReO(OH)L₂] : Biguanidium acid sulphate (or its methyl derivative equivalent) (2.5 g, 0.0125 mol) made alkaline with NaOH was added to a saturated aqueous solution of potassium hexachlororhenate (1 g, 0.002 mol). The resulting violet solution was exposed to air for 8-10 h for oxidation, when a rose crystalline solid [ReO(OH)(L)₂] separated

out. It was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and dried over fused calcium chloride; the compound being very slightly soluble in water.

$[\text{ReOCl}(\text{L})_2]$: $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{L}_2$ was treated with a saturated NH_4Cl solution when a yellow precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and dried over fused CaCl_2 ; the compound being insoluble in water and all common organic solvents.

$[\text{ReCl}_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: $\text{ReO}(\text{OH})_2\text{L}_2$ when treated with 8N HCl a blue solution was formed. Acetone was then added to the solution and the mixture evaporated over fused CaCl_2 in presence of solid KOH. The resulting blue crystals were washed with concentrated HCl followed by dry acetone under blanket of dry nitrogen and dried over fused CaCl_2 under reduced pressure; the compound being soluble in alcohols.

$[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: $[\text{ReCl}_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ on hydrolysis in water gave a brown solution, which on concentration under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 in presence of KOH, gave a buff coloured precipitate. It was filtered, washed with cold water and dry ethanol and dried as usual; the compound being soluble in water.

$[\text{Re}(\text{LH})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: K_2ReCl_6 (1 g, 0.002 mol) was mixed thoroughly with biguanide normal sulphate (3 g, 0.015 mol). The mixture was fused over a sand-bath at 165–70°. The fused mass was cooled, extracted with water and filtered. The rose violet residue was washed thoroughly with water and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 .

Conductivity measurements were made with a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. A Simadzu 210A spectrophotometer was used to record electronic spectra, and Perkin-Elmer 297 and 597 grating spectrophotometers were used to record ir spectra. μ_{eff} values were determined at 25° by Curie method. Re was estimated gravimetrically as nitronperrhenate⁸. The oxidation states or rhenium were determined by oxidation of rhenium to heptavalent states by hydrogen peroxide in the cold and back-titrating the excess hydrogen peroxide with a standard permanganate solution.

Results and Discussion

Coordinated hydroxyl group in the complex $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{L})_2]$ is replaced by chloride ion on treatment with NH_4Cl producing an electroneutral species characterised as $[\text{ReOCl}(\text{L})_2]$. $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{L})_2]$ which reacts with dilute HCl to produce $[\text{ReO}(\text{Cl})(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ containing protonated forms of biguanides. On treatment of $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{L})_2]$ with concentrated HCl in acetone, Cl^- replaces the hydroxyl and the oxygen producing $[\text{ReCl}_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

The neutral complexes $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{L})_2]$ and $[\text{ReOCl}(\text{L})_2]$ are insoluble in water, whereas ionic

complexes $[\text{ReOCl}(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{ReCl}_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Re}(\text{OH})_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ are soluble in water, ethanol and methanol. $[\text{ReCl}_2(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ is also soluble in acetone. Conductivity and elemental analyses (Table 1) data indicate the presence of deprotonated biguanides in the case of neutral complexes, whereas in all the ionic complexes the biguanide molecules are present as protonated form. Conductivity data indicate hydrolysis of $[\text{ReOCl}(\text{LH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ in aqueous solution.

All the complexes except $[\text{Re}(\text{BigH})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are diamagnetic, the latter being weakly paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 0.74$ B.M.). Diamagnetism arises due to tetragonal distortion of the octahedral field. Besides the usual deformation caused by the presence of non-equivalent ligands, there is a small distortion due to non-uniform occupancy of t_{2g} level. Again the $d\pi-p\pi$ overlap which is stronger for oxygen than for biguanide, further destabilises the t_{2g} level to such an extent that the d_{xy} orbital become the lowest energy orbital and accommodate the two electrons with their spin paired. These observations are in conformity with the results obtained by other workers^{4,5}.

The weak paramagnetism observed in the complex $[\text{Re}(\text{LH})_3](\text{SO}_4)_{1.5} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be due to its dinuclear nature involving SO_4 bridging and its Re-Re interaction as observed in other cases^{6,7}.

The ir spectrum of biguanide hydrochloride shows broad band at 3400–3000 cm^{-1} due to ν_{NH} ⁸⁻¹⁰ which becomes sharp and shifts to lower frequency (3350–3240 cm^{-1}) in the complexes. The bands in the region (1680–1650 cm^{-1}) for all the metal complexes and the ligand hydrochloride are due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ mode coupled with NH deformation and OH deformation modes^{9,10}. In metal complexes, the lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ occurs due to lowering of C=N bond order on coordination with N atom¹². At 1170 cm^{-1} the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of CNH_2 groups appear in all the complexes¹². The asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of $\nu_{\text{N-C-N}}$ ^{10,11} occur at 1680 and 1580 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the ligand. In the metal complexes, these bands shift to lower frequencies at 1620 and 1560 cm^{-1} , respectively. $\nu_{\text{Re=O}}$ bands for the oxo complexes $[\text{ReOX}(\text{L})_2]$ and $[\text{ReOX}(\text{LH})_2]\text{X}_2$ appear at 990–980 cm^{-1} (Ref. 13). The medium intensity $\nu_{\text{Re-O}}$ ^{5,14} bands appear at 935–920 cm^{-1} in the chloro and oxochloro complexes. The band at 920 cm^{-1} in the hydroxo complexes is attributed to $\nu_{\text{Re-OH}}$ ^{5,15}. Bands at 750 cm^{-1} arise out of Re-OH deformation modes. The strong band at 490 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{Re-N}}$. Four out of the six coordination sites of the distorted octahedral geometry around rhenium are occupied by nitrogen atoms of the two biguanide ligands, both in the neutral and in the ionic forms. In the oxo complexes, one of the remaining two positions is occupied by oxygen and the other by chloride or hydroxyl ion. In the chloro complexes, however, these two positions are occupied by two chloride ions. In the tris-biguanide complex, biguanide in

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF Re COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_m^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	Re	N	Cl/SO ₄	
[ReOOH(Big) ₂]	43.90 (44.42)	33.05 (33.39)	-	-
[ReOCl(Big) ₂]	43.32 (42.54)	32.17 (31.98)	8.20 (8.09)	-
[ReOCl(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	35.81 (36.47)	27.48 (27.41)	20.42 (20.82)	324 ^{a, c}
[ReCl ₂ (BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	32.24 (32.93)	24.84 (24.75)	31.54 (31.34)	330 ^b
[Re(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ ²	34.70 (35.23)	26.45 (26.48)	19.92 (20.11)	340 ^a
[ReO(OH)(MeBig) ₂]	41.34 (41.64)	31.30 (31.30)	-	-
[ReOCl(MeBig) ₂]	38.76 (39.99)	30.19 (30.06)	7.54 (7.61)	-
[ReOCl(MeBigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	34.24 (34.57)	26.36 (25.99)	19.45 (19.74)	320 ^{a, c}
[ReCl ₂ (MeBigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	30.56 (31.37)	23.25 (23.58)	29.41 (29.86)	325 ^b
[Re(BigH) ₂](SO ₄) _{1.5} · 7H ₂ O ^d	24.25 (24.52)	27.83 (27.65)	18.94 (18.96)	-

*Big = Biguanide, MeBig = methyl biguanide; ^d% loss at 120°: Found 16.20 (Calcd. 16.59).

**In solvent: ^awater, ^bMeOH; ^chydrolysed.

the protonated form offers bidentate chelation and all the six coordination sites are occupied by biguanide nitrogen atom.

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Mechanism of Oxidation of Propan-1-ol and Butan-1-ol by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) using Ruthenium(VIII) Oxide as a Homogeneous Catalyst

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OSMIUM tetroxide catalysed oxidation of methanol and ethanol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) was first reported by Krishna and Singh¹ along with the oxidation of mandalate ion². Recently, osmium tetroxide has been replaced by ruthenium tetroxide and its catalytic activity was studied by Tandon and Krishna³. Ruthenium(VIII) oxide has been reported to catalyse the oxidation of diols by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III)⁴, but the oxidation of alcohols catalysed by ruthenium(VIII)